

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Graphical representation of the effect of the indium activity on the radiolabeling efficiency

Figure a1. The labeling efficiency as function of the indium activity. The samples were prepared in HEPES buffer pH 7.4 with 0.8 mM tropolone and 50 kBq ^{111}In activity, with the exception of the lowest data point, for which 5 kBq was used, containing 4.3 mg/mL PS-b-PEO micelles. Increasing amounts of non-radioactive indium has been added equivalent to an ^{111}In activity up to 500 MBq. The uncertainty bars are the standard deviations (N=3).